

Kinetics and mechanistic study of permanganatic oxidation of pyrazinamide in acidic media

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Abstract : The oxidation of pyrazinamide by potassium permanganate in acidic media was studied spectrophotometrically at 525 nm. It was found to be zero order with respect to oxidant, fractional order with respect to hydrogen ion concentration and first order with respect to substrate. The average (ΔG^\ddagger) was found to be 87.60 kJ mol⁻¹. The values ΔS^\ddagger was found to be -0.2132 kJ mol⁻¹ and energy of activation was found to be 23.95 kJ mol⁻¹. A suitable mechanism is proposed based on the experimental conditions.

Keywords : Kinetics study, permanganatic oxidation, pyrazinamide.

Introduction

Pyrazinamide (PZA) (pyrazine-2-carboxamide) is used in combination with other drugs like isoniazid, rifampicin in the treatment of tuberculosis¹.

PZA is an analogue of nicotinamide which is vitamin B₃. The PZA has an excellent sterilizing effect on semi dormant tubercle bacilli and when used in combination with rifampicin, has helped in shortening the duration of treatment². The pharmaco-kinetic study of PZA reveals that, it gets rapidly absorbed ($t_{\max} \leq 1$ h) and showed a short distribution phase followed by an elimination phase³ of $t_{1/2\beta} = 9.6$ h. The long term use of PZA develop hepatotoxicity though some herbs were found to be effective in preventing hepatotoxicity partially⁴. The oxidation of amide is difficult because of its inertness towards electrophilic oxidants⁵.

When PZA is administered to human, 5-hydroxy pyrazinamides is found to be major urinary metabolite⁶. The OH⁻ radicals produced in the H₂O₂/UV and γ -radiation process oxidises acetamide (CH₃CONH₂) into first oxamic acid (HCOOCONH₂) and ending in complete mineralization with the production of nitrates⁷. The *in vitro* study reveals that oxidation of PZA by an enzyme

aldehyde oxidase converts it into 5-hydroxy pyrazinamides⁸. It was reported that PZA when introduced orally or intraperitoneally shows marked increase in NAD⁺ content in rat liver. This increase in NAD⁺ was brought about by a metabolite of PZA which gives different mechanism i.e. glutarate pathway for conversion of tryptophan⁹ to NAD⁺.

Kinetic procedure : The reactions were allowed to occur in glass stoppered Erlenmeyer flask of coning make. These flasks were suspended in a water bath with a temperature sensitivity of 0.1 °C. The reaction mixture except substrate was prepared by taking all reaction ingredients. The temperature pre-equilibrated solution of substrate was added into the reaction mixture and the time of initiation of the reaction was recorded when half of the contents of pipette were released. The reaction mixtures were shaken and aliquot (1 ml) was taken out at different time intervals and absorbance of unreacted KMnO₄ was noted at $\lambda_{\max} = 525$ nm. The reaction rate was calculated by drawing pseudo-first order plot, [substrate] > [KMnO₄] condition. Straight lines were obtained and pseudo-first order rate constants were calculated in the usual manner. These rate constants exhibit reproducibility within 5%.

Product analysis :

Known volume of 0.1 M substrate and 0.01 M KMnO₄ in 1 M H₂SO₄ solution were taken in 250 ml beaker and kept for 4–5 days for completion of the reaction. The diethyl ether was added into the reaction mixture and then it was shaken for an hour before separating two layers. The ethereal layer was taken on the watch glass and was left for some time for evaporation of ether. The residue left on the watch glass and air dried before identification. The solid mass was identified by m.p. determination and IR spectra. The IR spectra of PZA and the product obtained was compared. It gives value for PZA :

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3026 (-OH stretching), 1700 (C stretching).

The product obtained was pyrazinoic acid with melting point 223 °C and shows IR frequencies :

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3100 (-OH stretching), 1720 (C stretching).

Experimental kinetic results

Dependence of permanganate concentration : To study the effect of dependence of permanganate concentration, the concentration of KMnO₄ was varied from 1 × 10⁻⁴ to 9 × 10⁻⁴ M, keeping constant concentration of other reaction ingredients such as substrate and acid. Since reaction has been studied under pseudo-first order condition, a plot of log [MnO₄⁻] versus time was made and pseudo-first order rate constant was calculated. These results are given in the Table 1. From the perusal of the results, it is clear that pseudo-first order rate constant do not change

Table 1. First order rate constant for oxidation

Sl. no.	10 ³ [PZA] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ⁴ [KMnO ₄] (mol dm ⁻³)	[H ₂ SO ₄] (mol dm ⁻³)	k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)
1.	1	1	1	0.0359
2.	1	2	1	0.027
3.	1	3	1	0.0323
4.	1	4	1	0.0305
5.	1	5	1	0.0216
6.	1	6	1	0.0354
7.	1	7	1	0.0424
8.	1	8	1	0.0207
9.	1	9	1	0.0311

with change in concentration of permanganate confirming the zero order dependence with respect to oxidant.

Dependence of substrate concentration : The concentration of substrate was varied from 1 × 10⁻³ to 9 × 10⁻³ M (Table 2). The pseudo-first order rate constants were calculated. This shows that order with respect to substrate is one.

Table 2. First order rate constant for oxidation

Sl. no.	10 ⁴ [PZA] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ⁴ [KMnO ₄] (mol dm ⁻³)	[H ₂ SO ₄] (mol dm ⁻³)	k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)
1.	1	1	1	0.0245
2.	2	1	1	0.0313
3.	3	1	1	0.0265
4.	4	1	1	0.0278
5.	5	1	1	0.027
6.	6	1	1	0.0285
7.	7	1	1	0.0286
8.	8	1	1	0.0305
9.	9	1	1	0.0387

The reaction was studied as a function of [PZA] at fixed [MnO₄⁻], [H₂SO₄] and temperature. The values of *k* increases with increase in [PZA]. A plot of *k* versus [PZA] is nonlinear passing through the origin.

The rate law describing the irreversible reaction between PZA and KMnO₄ was assumed to be in the form

$$-d [PZA]/dt = k [PZA]^\beta [KMnO_4]^\alpha$$

where $-d [PZA]/dt$ is the rate of reaction. [PZA] is the concentration of PZA in mol/dm³, [KMnO₄] is the concentration of KMnO₄ in mol/dm³ and α and β are the reaction orders with respect to each reactant. If the [PZA] is excess, its concentration is assumed to be constant over the entire reaction period, the rate law is reduced to

$$-d [PZA]/dt = r_{PZA} = k_1 [MnO_4^-]^\alpha$$

where *k*₁ is pseudo-first order rate constant.

Taking natural logarithm

$$\ln (-d [PZA]/dt) = \ln k_1 + \alpha \ln [KMnO_4^-]$$

Hence ln $(-d [PZA]/dt)$ against ln [KMnO₄⁻] gives a straight line with slope equal to order and intercept corresponds¹⁰ to ln *k*₁.

Dependence of acid concentration : The hydrogen ion concentration dependence was studied by employing H₂SO₄ at fixed [MnO₄⁻] and [substrate] respectively. The

plot of these rate constant against $[H^+]$ shows fractional order with respect to acid. Since the rate decreases with increase in $[H^+]$ ion, the deprotonated species of oxidant or substrate must involve in the reaction mechanism. The results are given in the Table 3.

Table 3. First order rate constant for oxidation

Sl. no.	10^3 [PZA] (mol dm ⁻³)	10^4 [KMnO ₄] (mol dm ⁻³)	[H ₂ SO ₄] (mol dm ⁻³)	k_{obs} (s ⁻¹)
1.	1	1	0.1	0.0326
2.	1	1	0.2	0.045
3.	1	1	0.3	0.0336
4.	1	1	0.4	0.0333
5.	1	1	0.5	0.0381
6.	1	1	0.6	0.0343
7.	1	1	0.7	0.0468
8.	1	1	0.8	0.0277
9.	1	1	0.9	0.0293

Effect of added salts : In the present investigation effect of salt on the rate of reaction is carried out. The salts selected are KCl, KBr and KI. These will give effect of anion particularly halides on the rate of reaction. The divalent and trivalent cationic salts were also used such as CaCl₂, Ca(NO₃)₂, MgCl₂, AlCl₃, Al(NO₃)₃ and K₂SO₄. The experiments were carried out under pseudo-first order condition taking 1×10^{-3} M PZA, 1 M H₂SO₄, 1×10^{-4} M KMnO₄ and varying the concentration of salts from 1×10^{-2} M to 9×10^{-2} M. These results were used to determine first order rate constant. The time curve obtained for these experiments were used to determined initial rate. The rate constants for the oxidation of PZA in presence of different salts are shown in Table 4.

From the table it is clear that, it does not show a specific trend with increase in concentration of salt with respect to almost all the salts except MgCl₂, where rate increase with increases in concentration of MgCl₂. For the rest of the salt the rate constant values show a trend : KI < KBr < KCl < K₂SO₄ < Ca(NO₃)₂ < CaCl₂ < MgCl₂ < Al(NO₃)₃ < AlCl₃.

Effect of temperature : The dependence of the reaction rate on temperature was investigated between 20 to 55 °C. Higher temperatures were not attempted for fear of decomposition of the compounds. The activation parameters (Table 5) of the reaction are calculated by a plot of log k versus $1/T$. The high negative value of ΔS^\ddagger indicates that interaction of reacting ions of similar charges to form an activated complex and is more ordered than the reactant due to loss of degree of freedom.

The changes in the rate are caused by changes in both ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger . A plot of ΔH^\ddagger versus ΔS^\ddagger is linear (Fig. 1) which follows equation,

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = \beta \Delta S^\ddagger$$

where β is called isokinetic temperature¹¹ and $\beta = 0.0205$. The entropy of activation ΔS^\ddagger for a group of MnO₄⁻ reactions is negative. For the reaction that proceed via complex formation i.e. the inner sphere mechanism, while ΔS^\ddagger values for the outer sphere reactions tend to more positive¹². Large negative values of ΔS^\ddagger can be attributed to the involvement of bulkier species¹³. These also indicate that the decomposition of activated complex is a slow process¹⁴. Although the rate law expression can not pro-

Table 4. Effect of added salt on first order rate constant

10^2 [Salt] (mol dm ⁻³)	Rate constants (s ⁻¹)								
	KCl	KBr	KI	K ₂ SO ₄	CaCl ₂	Ca(NO ₃) ₂	MgCl ₂	AlCl ₃	Al(NO ₃) ₃
1	0.0067	0.0084	0.005	0.004	0.0052	0.0312	-	0.0328	0.0239
2	0.0161	0.0025	0.004	0.0071	0.006	0.0293	0.0077	0.027	0.0281
3	0.0161	0.0024	0.001	0.0048	0.0121	0.0397	0.0061	0.0342	0.0254
4	0.0071	0.0023	0.001	0.009	0.0097	0.0232	0.0141	0.0376	0.0283
5	0.0119	0.001	0.003	0.0052	0.0047	0.0286	0.0162	0.008	0.0354
6	0.0068	0.0012	0.003	0.0102	0.0078	0.0351	0.0365	0.0093	0.0317
7	0.007	0.0009	0.002	0.015	0.0078	0.0271	0.0278	0.0046	0.0313
8	0.0054	0.0112	0.002	0.0278	0.0058	0.0328	0.0259	0.0076	0.0298
9	0.0051	0.0018	0.001	0.0115	0.008	0.0258	0.0069	0.0065	0.0409

[PZA] = 1×10^{-3} M, [KMnO₄] = 1×10^{-4} M and [H₂SO₄] = 1 M.

Table 5. Thermodynamic parameter
Activation energy $E_a = 23.95 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$

Sl. no.	Temp. (K)	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔS^\ddagger (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol^{-1})
1.	293	21.51	-0.2101	83.083
2.	298	21.47	-0.2113	84.465
3.	303	21.43	-0.2121	85.700
4.	308	21.39	-0.2126	86.882
5.	313	21.34	-0.2135	88.184
6.	318	21.30	-0.2143	89.471
7.	323	21.26	-0.2152	90.801
8.	328	21.22	-0.2164	92.229
Average		21.369	-0.2132	87.602

Fig. 1. Plot of ΔH against ΔS .

vide information about electron transfer process, whether it is of inner or outer sphere nature but some information can be drawn from the magnitude of rate constant and activation parameter¹⁵. The oxidation of PZA, when carried out at different temperatures, we found that ΔS^\ddagger is negative whereas ΔH^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger are positive. The negative value of ΔS^\ddagger indicates that compactness of the intermediate complex and are characteristics of one odd/or two electron inner sphere electron transfer. The positive values of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger are indicative of enhanced formation of intermediate with increase in temperature. It also indicates non spontaneity of the complex formation in the rate determining step¹⁶. Since k_{obs} values do not represent a single elementary step, more useful information from activation parameters can not be obtained¹⁷.

Mechanism :

In some organic oxidation reactions Mn^{II} acts as cata-

lyst¹⁸. It reacts with one of the reactant and converts to Mn^{III} . The Mn^{III} is a powerful oxidizing agent, which generally disproportionates to Mn^{II} and Mn^{IV} . But, it can be stabilized in acid medium and in presence of sulphate. The Mn^{III} can be used as oxidant for the chemiluminescence reagents for the determination of pharmaceuticals in tablet¹⁹.

The rate of oxidation by permanganate depends on several factors which include structure of the substrate, the acidity of the solutions, temperature and concentration of permanganate. It is established fact that permanganate undergoes three electron transfers in the pH range 3.5 to 12. In acidic condition, the three electron transfer²⁰ takes place as

The Mn^{2+} is expected to be one of the products. It will reduce MnO_4^- into Mn^{3+} and Mn^{4+} in presence of acid.

Hence if the primary oxidizing species is MnO_4^- , the rate of reactions decreases with addition of Mn^{2+} and if the oxidizing species is either Mn^{3+} or Mn^{4+} , the rate of oxidation increases²¹.

The mechanism of oxidation can be given as

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